

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL WORK IN THE EDUCATIONAL STRUCTURES OF THE MIA

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To implement the provisions of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2017, No. PP-3413 "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the Procedure for Working with Personnel of Internal Affairs Bodies and the Organization of Their Service," it is necessary to consider it an important part of personnel policy in organizing educational work with employees of internal affairs bodies.

Currently, the main goal of educational work is the formation of a professionally qualified, ethically and psychologically stable personality. At the same time, personal responsibility for the organization and conduct of educational work in educational structures falls on the heads of internal affairs bodies, their deputies, personnel and employees carrying out educational work.

Circumstances that negatively impact the evaluation of the activities of internal affairs bodies arise from shortcomings in the training of employees. These include the following shortcomings in the implementation of educational work in educational structures:

- lack of specialization of personnel working with educational work;
- unsatisfactory level of professionalism and knowledge of employees carrying out educational work;
- failure to objectively assess the circumstances by the staff engaged in upbringing (avoidance of punishment);
- the state of work in cooperation with psychological centers does not meet the requirements.

Today, one of the pressing tasks is to educate employees of the internal affairs system of our republic to be loyal to the region, people, and the state in which they live, and to increase their love for their homeland.

Veterans play a special role in the upbringing of employees of internal affairs bodies. The task of studying their experience and lessons in ensuring the safety of society, learning from them, and passing on to future generations is

becoming increasingly relevant due to the fact that their number is decreasing year after year.

It should be noted with satisfaction that veterans are people who deserve deep respect and respect. Because they have made a significant contribution to the protection of public order, the prevention of crimes and offenses that pose a threat to the people. It is important to use their life experience to increase the efficiency of the activities of employees of the internal affairs bodies, to strengthen the peace and defense of our country, to educate our employees.

To do this, the following principles must be followed:

the principle of intergenerational continuity in the organization of educational work is based on the improvement of forms and methods of youth upbringing through the organization of direct interaction between the older generation with the new generation, possessing life and professional experience. At the same time, it requires reliance not only on acquired experience, but also on theoretical knowledge.

the principle of historicity is based on the study of the combat activities of military commanders in all periods of historical development, the study of the behavior, behavior, knowledge and skills of military personnel from the rank of a soldier to the commander in chief;

the organization of educational work is based on the principle of cooperation with state bodies, public organizations, associations, and other social institutions. This is achieved through a team, the system of collective education is based on the strategy and tactics of preparing employees of internal affairs bodies for the defense of the Motherland. Only a collective can raise a highly responsible, well-rounded individual with a sense of love for the Motherland.

Based on the principles outlined above, educational work is organized on a solid foundation. At the same time, these principles are not a mandatory rule, but part of a comprehensive approach. After all, a comprehensive approach to organizing educational work in educational structures appears as a means of optimizing education, improving the moral-political, psychological, technical-tactical, and physical training of young people. It requires, on the one hand, the listed aspects of education, and on the other hand, its interaction with ideological-political, labor, and moral education.

An important condition for using a comprehensive approach is the development of criteria for evaluating the level of organization of educational work. This level of consciousness of listeners and cadets is manifested through

ideological beliefs, a sense of patriotism, as well as a system of political, military-technical, and physical training, as well as economic interest.

Unfortunately, sometimes the organization of educational work in educational structures is assessed unilaterally. In this case, attention is paid only to specific aspects of the organization of educational work, without taking into account the state of physical and military-technical training. Indicators of the organization of educational work are manifested in the high moral and political readiness of young people, their activity in studying exercises, and their participation in mass sports. One of our main goals in this regard is to cultivate in every person the qualities of love for the Motherland, dedicating all their strength and energy for it, pride in their glory, name, and position.

Education and upbringing are one of the important vital factors in achieving a sense of patriotism and loyalty to the Motherland among employees of internal affairs bodies. Our ancestors from ancient times considered knowledge, education, and upbringing, which are invaluable spiritual wealth, the most fundamental condition and guarantee of human perfection and the development of the nation.

To implement a comprehensive approach to organizing educational work, it is necessary to generalize the experience of educational work. In this process, the scientific rules and practical conclusions of science play an important role. It helps to master the laws, structure, and mechanisms of the educational process, the theory and methodology of patriotic work, as well as principles and organizational forms.

Military education and upbringing play an important role in organizing educational work in educational structures.

Education is the process of forming and developing the individual's consciousness in accordance with the goals and objectives of a particular society, a set of all influences aimed at actively engaging people in socio-economic and cultural life.

Family, various public organizations, science, technology, literature, art, mass media, radio and television, and various propaganda activities have an effective impact on education and upbringing.

Educational and upbringing in the institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs system is one of the effective factors in raising the general military spirit, raising them to be steadfast and courageous, popularizing the military knowledge inherited from our ancestors, teaching the secrets of military combat art.

It is known from history that the Turkic peoples at one time had the most powerful armies in the whole world, such great commanders as Amir Timur had grown up, military strategy and tactics were carefully and perfectly developed.[2]

Regardless of the sphere of education, studying its history, the experience of our ancestors, their teachings and teachings in this regard is of great importance for today's educator. In order to be a teacher-educator, to cultivate the intellect of others, to benefit from the enlightenment, to raise them as true patriots, the educator himself must meet such high requirements, possess such great qualities.

It is necessary to study the content of the concept of education in the educational structures of the internal affairs bodies, its connection and prospects with education in general. It is important to determine the practical significance of this issue, not the theoretical aspect.

Therefore, in the process of teaching not only ideological, social, economic, moral, and ideological foundations, but also military disciplines in the internal affairs bodies, with the strengthening of mastering the secrets of military equipment and weapons, it is also important to educate employees in the spirit of patriotism as a military socio-political direction in our military education.

To enhance the effectiveness of organizing educational work in educational structures under the Ministry of Internal Affairs, it is necessary to summarize the experience of work in this area. In this regard, the scientific rules and practical conclusions of pedagogy play an important role. It contributes to knowledge of the laws, structure, and mechanisms of the educational process, mastery of the theory and methodology of patriotic work, as well as principles and organizational forms.

In conclusion, one of the priority tasks is to educate in the spirit of serving the Motherland and the people in the educational structures of the internal affairs bodies.

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